

9A Study on the Needs of Old Age Home in Kokrajhar Town

Aroti Basumatary

Kokrajhar Govt.College, Deptt.of Education, Email- arotibasumatary332gmail.com

Argeng Narzary

Asstt.Prof. Deptt. of Bodo, Sapatgram College, Email-argengnarzary1122@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

An old age home is a residential facility with nursing and assisted living facilities designed for older adults who do not have home to live and no one to care for them at older age. An old age home provide for them safety and security to access better healthcare services and to have better comfortable life. **Objective:** To Study about the needs of Old Age Home. **Method:** Descriptive survey method was adopted for the present study. **Conclusion:** In conclusion we can say that an old age home is a great important in the present society for senior citizens for safety and security and for living a comfortable life.

1. Introduction

An old age home is known as retirement home, old folks' home or nursing home. It is a place for those old people who do not have home to live. This place is like a home where they get every facilities designed for older adults for living like-food, clothes, medical care, housekeeping and recreational activities to maintain their quality of life. The old age home is like a community where older people live with other people when they have been abandoned by their families. Even though it is a good home for them but still it cannot take the place of a real home. Most of the people live abroad and their old parents are left alone, no one to take care of them. They are easily target for criminals. In this case old age home gives a protection and security to them. At old age homes people are more or less of same age group. So, it is easy for everyone to get comfortable with each other. The staffs are in-charge of feeding them in time and taking care of their every need. They take good care of them. Old age home may be blessing for

some people. Old age home is the last hope of those people so they must be equipped with better facilities so that these people can live a better life. The purpose of the old age home is to provide safe and secure for those people who have nowhere else to go and live, no one to support them in their needs. Old age home in India may be of two types either privately owned or operated by the government or non-profit organisation.

History of old age home

The first old age home in India is Raja Varma Old Age Home in Thrissur, Kerala founded in 1911 by Raja of Cochin. In 1840, The Friend in Need Society of Madras was the first voluntary organisation to care for the old aged people (Cherian M.2015.The new of Old Age Homes. Civil Society).In India old age homes vary. According to Wishes and Blessings, India got approximately 728 old age homes, predominantly set up by NGOs in 2022, 750 old age homes in India by Shibasram and around 1,150old age homes according to A Tata Trusts, Samarth and United Nations Population Fund (UNPFA)(Sani B.(2024).Old Age Homes in India. First Report News.). There are some options of staying in old age home in India. This are-

Option of old age home	Numbers of Homes
Free homes	325
Pay and Stay homes	95
Home with both free and pay and stay facilities	116
Home for the sick	278
Home exclusively for women	101
Total	915

Source: Total old age homes in India (NET).

Kerela got the highest old age homes in India with 124 in numbers, Second Odisha with 91 senior citizen homes. In Assam there are 40 numbers of old age home. As on date a total of 35 senior citizen homes are operational under IPSeC(Integrated Programme for Senior Citizens) in the State of Assam, with a total capacity of 1,145 indigent senior citizens and one senior citizen home is maintained by the State Government. Details are given at Annexure 1. (Shri Ajit Kumar Bhuyan, 2022, Operation of Old Age Homes by NGO in Assam).

Kokrajhar is one of the Districts of Bodoland Territorial Region. It is the capital city of BTR. Kokrajhar town is a part under Kokrajhar District. In Kokrajhar town till now there is only one old age home. This is located in Chorikhola near Kokrajhar Town, with Re.gd No.-Rs/KJR/253/U/18-20-21. The name of the old age home is **Shanti Old Age Home**. The total numbers of old people are 12; there are 5 men's and 7 women.

Importance of Old Age Home

- i) Old age is importance to provide secure and comfortable living for the elderly people.
- ii) To provide medical care and nursing support for those chronic illness or disabilities.
- ii) To offer recreational activities, social events and companionship to prevent social isolation and promote mental health.
- iv) To help elderly person to develop a sense of self-confidence and self-reliance.
- v) To create homely environment with care and compassion they deserve.
- vi) To implement policies and welfare programmes in favour of senior citizens, as approved by the government of India.

Need of Old Age Home

Nowadays most of the people have one child or childless or she never married or divorce or widows. There is often news about the elderly persons that they are being neglected or abused by their own children. In such cases an old age home is a better option for them, than living alone or staying under someone else's roof or depression. The need of old age home is not just another urban phenomenon. The breakup of the joint family has isolated the elderly in both urban and rural areas. Most of the elderly, whether rural or urban, face the empty nest syndrome' when their children leave in search of work opportunities or better living conditions and lifestyles. They might choose to migrate out of the country or shift to a different city.

In Kokrajhar Town also the investigator found many people who are helpless and homeless at their old age. So, the investigator felt the need of more old age home to provide safe and secure for those people who have no home to go and live and no one to support them in their needs at their old age.

2. Objectives

- i) To identify the key reasons leading to the needs of Old Age Home in Kokrajhar Town.
- ii) To suggest measures for the establishment of more old age homes to ensure safety, care and dignity for the elderly people in Kokrajhar Town.

3. Method

Descriptive survey method is adopted for the present study.

i) Population

The present study comprised of all the old age people both male and female from five areas under Kokrajhar Town, three areas under Kokrajhar Municipal Board City i.e Ward No.-4 Habrubari, Ward No.- 5 Hatimata, & Ward No.-7 Baganshali and Two Village areas i.e South Dimalgaon and Choraichola (Old Age Home Centre). The details of population is shown in the table below-

Table No. -1 Showing the population of the present study.

Name of the Areas	No. of Citizens
Habrubari	15
Hatimata	30
Baganshali	12
South Dimalgaon	17
Choraichola (Old Age Home Center)	12
Total	86

Source: Investigator 2024

ii) Samples

Purposive Sampling method will be used to select the sample. The present study comprised of 50 old age people both male and female from Kokrajhar Town. The details of sample are shown in the table below-

Table No. -2 showing the sample of the present study.

Name of the Areas	No. of Citizens
Habrubari	10

Hatimata	10
Baganshali	10
South Dimalgaon	10
Choraichola (Old Age Home Center)	10
Total	50

Source: Investigator 2024

iii) Data collected procedure

The Data is collected both from Primary and Secondary source. A questionnaire of 10 inquiries were prepared by the investigator and presented to the sample. Data were analyzed by the Percentage of the respondent.

iv) Tools

The investigator used self-constructed questionnaire for data collection.

v) Delimitation

1. Only Five areas under Kokrajhar Town are taken.
2. Three under Kokrajhar Municipal Board City i.e Ward No.-4, 5 & 7 and two Village areas.

4. Finding and Result

4.1. Response regarding the knowledge about old age home.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	35	70%
2	No.	15	30%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 70% of the respondents have knowledge about old age home and 30% of the respondents do not have.

Figure No.1 A pie-chart showing responses having knowledge about old age home

4.2. Response regarding family members force to go and stay at old age home.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	19	38%
2	No.	31	62%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is seen that 38% of the respondents feel that their family members force to go and stay at old age home and 62% of the respondents do not feel.

4.3. Response regarding family members care for them.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	28	56%
2	No.	22	44%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 56% of the respondents feel that their family members care for them and 44% of the respondents do not feel.

4.4. Response regarding old age people thinks that they are burden for their family members.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	16	32%
2	No.	34	68%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 32% of the respondents feel that they are burden for their family members and 68% of the respondents do not feel.

4.5. Response regarding prefer to go old age home when they are old.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	20	40%
2	No.	30	60%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 40% of the respondents prefer to go old age home when they are old and 60% of the respondents do not prefer.

Figure No.2 showing the Response regarding prefer to go old age home when they are old.

4.6. Response regarding importance to have old age home.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	37	74%
2	No.	13	26%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is seen that 74% of the respondents feel the importance of having old age home and only 26% of the respondents do not feel.

Figure No.3 showing the Response regarding importance to have old age home.

4.7. Response regarding necessary of counselling programme for old age people in old age home.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	38	76%
2	No.	12	24%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 76% of the respondents feel necessary of counselling programme for old age people in old age home and 24% of the respondents do not feel.

4.8. Response regarding the need of separate old age home for man and women.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	45	90%
2	No.	5	10%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 90% of the respondents feel the need of separate old age home for man and women and only 10% of the respondents do not feel.

4.9. Response regarding sufficient treatment they get in old age home.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	27	54%
2	No.	23	46%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 54% of the respondents feel they get sufficient treatment in old age home and 46% of the respondents do not feel.

Figure No.4 showing the Response regarding sufficient treatment they get in old age home.

4.10. Response regarding the need of old age home in Kokrajhar District.

Sl.No.	Responses		Percentage
1	Yes	45	90%
2	No.	05	10%
3	Total	50	100%

From the above table it is found that 90% of the respondents feel the need of old age home in Kokrajhar District and only 10% of the respondents do not feel.

Figure No.5 showing the Response regarding the need of old age home in Kokrajhar District.

Suggestions

- i) People should have awareness about old age home.
- ii) Better environment should be created in old age home.

- iii) Better medical facilities should be provided in old age home.
- iv) Well trained staff should be ensure to take care for them.
- v) Government should set up more programmes where community members, youth groups volunteer can easily interact with old age people in old age home.
- vi) For house design of the old age home there should be ramp to climb instead of stairs. Proper lighting, safety bathroom, provide large doors both in the rooms and bathroom.
- vii) The Government should set up more old age home for the better living condition of the old age people.

5. Conclusion.

In conclusion we can say that, as old age home can provide many benefits for senior citizens. From the study it reveals that there is a need of old age home in Kokrajhar Town also so more old age home should be established for the better living conditions of the old age people of this areas .Thus old age home is a great important in the present society for senior citizens for living a comfortable life.

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